

**The RED criterion for fatigue life assessment of metals
under non-proportional loading**

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ABSTRACT

In the present paper, a novel criterion for fatigue life assessment of engineering components under multiaxial low-cycle fatigue regime is proposed. The criterion, named Refined Equivalent Deformation (RED) criterion, allows to take into account, when the load is non-proportional, the fatigue strength decrease experimentally observed for those metals sensitive to non-proportionality. The criterion is applied to two different metals (304 stainless steel and 6061 aluminum alloy) characterised by different non-proportional sensitivities. The accuracy of such a criterion is compared with those of other criteria available in the literature.

KEYWORDS: 304 stainless steel, 6061 aluminum alloy, critical plane, non-proportional, RED criterion

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the properties of loading that may have a relevant effect on the fatigue process of metallic materials is the non-proportionality of fatigue loading [1]. Such a non-proportionality occurs when the multiaxial load components change in a non-proportional manner. This is the case of either periodical components phase shifted, with different frequencies, with a given mean value, or random components. In this group, the block loads are included, that is, the loading sequence consisting of different types of loads.

The effect of the non-proportionality of loading has to be taken into account from the point of view of both load analysis and material properties, although different materials show different susceptibilities to the same loading non-proportional degree. Since such an effect cannot be underestimated in engineering practice, the research on fatigue non-proportional loading condition is at a stage of dynamic development [2-10].

The non-proportionality of loading influences the microstructure of metals. As a matter of fact, the non-proportional changing of fatigue loading components usually results in a non-proportional stress and strain state, where such

a state produces the rotation of the principal axes of stresses and strains. As a result, shear stresses acting in multiple directions activate more slip systems with respect to those under uniaxial and multiaxial proportional loading [11-13]. This great number of activated slip systems produces: increase of the dislocations interaction [14], high dislocation density [12], uniform dislocations distribution [12] where the dislocations remain inside each grain [11,15], the formation of dislocation cells of small sizes [11], great disorientation angle between the cells [16] and great sharpness of cell walls [16,17].

Such a mechanism of dislocations evolution causes an additional cyclic hardening of the material, that is, additional stress is required to reach the same level of strain under non-proportional loading with respect to proportional one. Moreover, the above mechanism is the main cause of the fatigue strength/fatigue limit decrease, in such a case the fatigue damage accumulation being increased with respect to that under proportional loading.

It is worth noting that different metals react in different ways to a given fatigue loading characterised by a certain degree of non-proportionality. This behaviour can be described as the sensitivity of the materials to non-proportional fatigue loading.

Different parameters are available in the literature to quantify the material sensitivity to non-proportional fatigue loading [1]: for example, the Stacking Fault Energy (SFE), the additional cyclic hardening coefficient α , and the ratio $\tau_{af,-1}/\sigma_{af,-1}$

between fully reversed shear strength and fully reversed normal strength.

As far as SFE is concerned, high values of this parameter are typical of materials where the mechanism of dislocation evaluation is the same under proportional and non-proportional loading, whereas the opposite occurs for low values of SFE.

As far as α is concerned, such a parameter can be determined through the equivalent stress σ_{eq}^{np} for a sinusoidal loading with a phase shift equal to 90° and the equivalent stress σ_{eq}^p under proportional loading, both calculated at the same stabilised phase: $\alpha = \frac{\sigma_{eq}^{np}}{\sigma_{eq}^p} - 1$. The higher the α value, the greater the

material sensitivity to non-proportional loading.

Finally, when the ratio $\tau_{af,-1}/\sigma_{af,-1}$ is lower than $1/\sqrt{3}$, it is proved that the material is sensitive to non-proportional loading.

The values of SFE, α , and $\tau_{af,-1}/\sigma_{af,-1}$ are correlated to each other [1]. More precisely:

- values of $\tau_{af,-1}/\sigma_{af,-1}$ approaching 0.5, correlate with $\alpha=0.8\div 1.0$ and with low values of SFE;
- values of $\tau_{af,-1}/\sigma_{af,-1}$ approaching 0.6, correlate with $\alpha=0.15\div 0.3$;
- values of $\tau_{af,-1}/\sigma_{af,-1}$ approaching 1.0, correlate with high values of SFE.

In the context of life assessment of engineering components under multiaxial low-cycle fatigue regime, the present paper

proposes a novel criterion, named Refined Equivalent Deformation (RED) criterion, that allows to take into account, when the load is non-proportional, the fatigue strength decrease for those materials sensitive to non-proportionality.

The accuracy of the criterion is assessed by analysing two experimental campaigns performed on 304 stainless steel and 6061 aluminum alloy [18,19], characterised by different non-proportional sensitivities.

The paper is structured as follows. The RED criterion is presented in **Section 2**, and the experimental campaigns here examined are described in **Section 3**. Then, the results and discussion are reported in **Section 4**. The main conclusions are summarised in **Section 5**.

2. THE REFINED EQUIVALENT DEFORMATION (RED) CRITERION

The RED criterion is a strain-based criterion, which is based on the critical plane concept. The criterion framework is shown in **Figure 1**, and the steps to be followed are hereafter detailed.

Figure 1

2.1 Material sensitivity to non-proportional loading

As has been previously mentioned, different metals have different sensitivities to a given degree of loading non-proportionality.

In the present criterion, the parameter used to quantify such a sensitivity is the ratio $\tau_{af,-1}/\sigma_{af,-1}$. When such a ratio is lower

than or equal to $1/\sqrt{3}$, the material is considered as sensitive to non-proportional loading: therefore, a possible decrease in fatigue strength/fatigue life has to be taken into account. On the other hand, when such a ratio is higher than $1/\sqrt{3}$, no effect produced by non-proportional loading has to be considered in the fatigue life assessment, and the criterion proposed by the present authors in Ref. [20] can be directly applied.

2.2 Critical plane determination

The critical plane Δ is determined according to the method proposed in Ref. [20], hereafter outlined.

For the sake of simplicity, let us consider a biaxial fatigue loading. The strain tensor at a material point P located on the surface of a smooth engineering component has the following strain

components: ε_r , ε_t , ε_z and $\frac{1}{2}\gamma_{zt}$, with respect to a fixed frame rtz .

Such a frame has its origin at point P, the r - and t -axis are perpendicular and tangent to the component surface, respectively, whereas the z -axis forms an orthogonal frame together r and t .

The components ε_r and ε_t are functions of ε_z by means of the effective Poisson's ratio ν_{eff} .

The principal strains ε_1 , ε_2 and ε_3 ($\varepsilon_1 \geq \varepsilon_2 \geq \varepsilon_3$) and the corresponding directions are computed during the observation time T , by identifying the instant when ε_1 attains its maximum value during T . Its direction, named \hat{l} , is used to determine the normal

\mathbf{w} to the critical plane: as a matter of fact, \mathbf{w} is assumed to form an angle δ with respect to $\hat{1}$, where such a rotation is performed from $\hat{1}$ to $\hat{3}$, $\hat{3}$ being the direction of ε_3 when ε_1 is maximum. The angle δ is computed as follows:

$$\delta = \frac{3}{2} \left\{ 1 - \left[\frac{1}{2(1+\nu_{eff})} \frac{\gamma_a}{\varepsilon_a} \right]^2 \right\} 45^\circ \quad (1)$$

where ε_a and γ_a are respectively computed according to the tensile Manson-Coffin equation

$$\varepsilon_a = \frac{\sigma'_f}{E} (2N_f)^b + \varepsilon'_f (2N_f)^c \quad (2)$$

and the torsional Manson-Coffin equation

$$\gamma_a = \frac{\tau'_f}{G} (2N_f)^{b_0} + \gamma'_f (2N_f)^{c_0} \quad (3)$$

It is worth noting that the angle δ (Eq. (1)) is a function of the number of loading cycles to failure, N_f .

2.3 Damage parameter determination

Let us consider a local frame uvw (with origin at the abovementioned point P) attached to the critical plane Δ : the u -axis is defined by the intersection between the wz plane and Δ , whereas the v -axis forms an orthogonal frame together with u and w .

The displacement $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ of point P may be decomposed in a component $\boldsymbol{\eta}_N$, function of the strain tensor component $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_w$ along the normal to Δ , and a component $\boldsymbol{\eta}_C$, function of the strain tensor components γ_{wu} and γ_{wv} lying on Δ .

The amplitudes of $\boldsymbol{\eta}_N$ and $\boldsymbol{\eta}_C$ are computed: it is worth noticing that, having $\boldsymbol{\eta}_C$ different directions during the observation interval, the maximum rectangular hull method [21] is used to compute its amplitude.

According to the RED criterion, the damage parameter is defined by the following equivalent deformation amplitude for non-proportional loading (named refined equivalent deformation amplitude, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{RED,a}^{np}$, in the following) [22]:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{eq,a}^{np} = (1 + k \sin |45^\circ - \varphi_i|) (1 + \alpha \Phi_i) \sqrt{(\eta_{N,a})^2 + \left(\frac{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_a}{\boldsymbol{\gamma}_a}\right)^2 (\eta_{C,a})^2} \quad (4)$$

and by the following parameter for proportional loading [20]:

$$\varepsilon_{eq,a}^p = \sqrt{(\eta_{N,a})^2 + \left(\frac{\varepsilon_a}{\gamma_a}\right)^2 (\eta_{C,a})^2} \quad (5)$$

where $\eta_{N,a}$ and $\eta_{C,a}$ are the amplitudes of η_N and η_C , respectively.

The definition of $\varepsilon_{RED,a}$ is in line with that employed by the Reduced Strain Range Method, proposed by Borodii et al. [23-25], also summarised in Ref. [22]. Moreover, it is worth noticing that Eq. (5) is used in the case of metals non sensitive to non-proportional loading, for which $k=0$ and $\alpha=0$ can be assumed (see **Figure 1**).

The parameter k is a material constant, which is representative of the material sensitivity to the change of fatigue properties, determined from uniaxial strain paths with respect to those determined from multiaxial proportional ones for the same strain amplitude. The parameter φ_i is the angle formed by the i -th non-proportional strain path with respect to the abscissa axis in the plane $\varepsilon_z - \gamma_{zt}/\sqrt{3}$. The computations of k and φ_i are reported in **Sub-Section 2.4**.

The additional cyclic hardening coefficient α is a material constant. Further, Φ_i is the coefficient of non-proportionality of the i -th non-proportional strain path. The computation of α and Φ_i is reported in **Sub-Section 2.5**.

2.4 k and φ_i computation

The material constant k is computed by considering only uniaxial strain paths:

$$k = \frac{1}{P} \sum_{j=1}^P k_j \quad (6)$$

with

$$k_j = \frac{1}{\text{sen}45^\circ} \left(\frac{\varepsilon_a(N_{exp,j})}{\varepsilon_{eq,a}^P} - 1 \right) \quad (7)$$

where P is the total number of uniaxial strain paths examined, $\varepsilon_a(N_{exp,j})$ is determined through Eq. (2) by replacing N_f with the experimental number $N_{exp,j}$ of loading cycles obtained for the j -th uniaxial strain path, and $\varepsilon_{eq,a}^P$ is computed by Eq. (5).

The parameter k is representative of the material sensitivity to the fatigue properties changing from uniaxial to multiaxial proportional loading: when $k_j > 0$, it means that for the j -th strain path the material manifests the above sensitivity; when $k_j \leq 0$, the material does not manifest such a sensitivity for the j -th strain path, and k_j can be assumed equal to zero.

Eq. (7) used to compute such a material constant is conceptually similar to that proposed by Borodii et al. **[23-25]**,

that involves: (i) instead of the Manson-Coffin equation (Eq. (2)), the $\Delta\varepsilon_{ASME}-N_f$ curve equation $(N_f = \left(\frac{\Delta\varepsilon_{ASME}}{10^B}\right)^n$ with $N_f = N_{exp,j}$) related to the material principal direction (as defined in **Refs [23-25]**), and (ii) instead of $\varepsilon_{eq,a}^p$ (Eq. (5)), the strain range $\Delta\varepsilon_{ASME}$ [26] of the proportional strain path characterised by an orientation different from the material principal direction. It is worth noticing that, in the first formulation of the RED criterion [22], $\varepsilon_{eq,a}^p$ in Eq. (7) was replaced by $\Delta\varepsilon_{ASME}$.

In order to measure the angle φ_i , the direction of the i -th non-proportional strain path has to be determined. Such a direction is defined as the segment, with the maximum length (named $\Delta\varepsilon_m$ in the following), that joints two points on the strain path in the $\varepsilon_z-\gamma_{yz}/\sqrt{3}$ plane. The angle φ_i is measured between the above segment and the abscissa axis in such a plane. Note that, in the first formulation of the RED criterion [22], φ_i was measured with respect to the material principal direction [23-25].

2.5 α and Φ_i computation

The material constant α is determined by considering only non-proportional strain paths as follows:

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \alpha_i \quad (8)$$

with

$$\alpha_i = \frac{1}{\Phi_i} \left(\frac{\varepsilon_a(N_{exp,i})}{\varepsilon_{eq,a}^p} - 1 \right) \quad (9)$$

where M is the total number of the non-proportional strain paths examined, $\varepsilon_a(N_{exp,i})$ is determined through Eq. (2) by replacing N_f with the experimental number $N_{exp,i}$ of loading cycles obtained for the i -th non-proportional strain path, and $\varepsilon_{eq,a}^p$ is computed by Eq. (5).

The parameter Φ_i is the coefficient of non-proportionality related to the i -th non-proportional strain path, and may be computed as is reported in the following, according to the method proposed by Borodii et al. [23-25]. When the non-proportional strain path in the $\varepsilon_z - \gamma_{zt}/\sqrt{3}$ plane is *convex* (that is, a *closed strain path* is considered), Φ_i is given by:

$$\Phi_i = \left(\frac{S_i}{S_{0,i}} \right)^{r_i} \quad (10)$$

where S_i is the area enveloped by the i -th convex path, whereas $S_{0,i}$ is the area of the smallest circle which contains the above path, in the $\varepsilon_z - \gamma_{zt}/\sqrt{3}$ plane.

The exponent r_i is given by:

$$r_i = 1 \quad (11)$$

for strain path represented by a smooth algebraic curve in the ε_z - $\gamma_{xz}/\sqrt{3}$ plane, and

$$r_i = \left(1 - \frac{S_i}{S_{0,i}}\right) \frac{l_i}{4\Delta\varepsilon_m} \quad (12)$$

for strain path represented by a piecewise broken line in the ε_z - $\gamma_{xz}/\sqrt{3}$ plane, being l_i the length of the convex path in such a plane.

When the non-proportional strain path in the ε_z - $\gamma_{xz}/\sqrt{3}$ plane is *non-convex* (that is, an *open strain path* is considered), Φ_i is given by:

$$\Phi_i = \left(\frac{S'_i}{S'_{0,i}}\right)^{r_i} \quad (13)$$

where S'_i is the area enveloped by an equivalent convex strain path containing the i -th one, whereas $S'_{0,i}$ is the area of the smallest circle which contains the above equivalent path, in the ε_z - $\gamma_{xz}/\sqrt{3}$ plane.

The exponent r_i is given by:

$$r_i = \frac{l_i}{4\Delta\varepsilon_m} \quad (14)$$

being l_i the length of the non-convex path in the $\varepsilon_z - \gamma_{zt}/\sqrt{3}$ plane.

The parameter α is representative of the material sensitivity to non-proportional loading: when $\alpha_i > 0$, it means that for the i -th strain path the material manifests the above sensitivity; when $\alpha_i \leq 0$, the material does not manifest such a sensitivity for the i -th strain path, and α_i can be assumed equal to zero.

Equation (9) used to compute such a material constant is conceptually similar to that proposed by Borodii et al. [23-25], that involves: (i) instead of the Manson-Coffin equation (Eq. (2)), the $\Delta\varepsilon_{ASME} - N_f$ curve equation, and (ii) instead of $\varepsilon_{eq,a}^p$ (Eq. (5)), the strain range $\Delta\varepsilon_{ASME}$ [26] of the non-proportional strain path. It is worth noticing that, in the first formulation of the RED criterion [22], $\varepsilon_{eq,a}^p$ in Eq. (9) was replaced by $\Delta\varepsilon_{ASME}$.

3. THE EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGNS EXAMINED

The first experimental campaign examined [18] was performed on a 304 stainless steel. Hollow cylindrical specimens were tested, whose sizes are reported in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2

A servo-hydraulic low cycle fatigue machine was used, and the testing was carried out under the von Mises' equivalent strain control. Push-pull tests and push-pull/reversed torsion tests, both proportional and non-proportional, were carried out, being the non-proportional ones characterised by a different strain path shape. Such paths are shown in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3

The ranges $\Delta\varepsilon_z$ and $\Delta\gamma_{zt}$ of the applied strains and the experimental number N_{exp} of loading cycles are listed in **Table 1**.

Table 1

Such a material is known to be characterised by a large additional cyclic hardening under non-proportional loading [18].

The second experimental campaign examined [19] was performed on a 6061 aluminum alloy. The sizes of the hollow cylindrical specimens tested are reported in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4

The testing machine used, the type of control, the type of loading and the path shapes were the same ones as those of the first experimental campaign being considered. The ranges $\Delta\varepsilon_z$ and

$\Delta\gamma_{zt}$ of the applied strains and the experimental number N_{exp} of loading cycles are listed in **Table 2**.

Table 2

Such a material is known to be characterised by a small additional cyclic hardening under non-proportional loading [19].

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the RED criterion (see **Figure 1**) some input data have to be set. Input data for the above 304 stainless steel are listed in **Table 3**, whereas those for the 6061 aluminum alloy are listed in **Table 4**.

Table 3

Table 4

More precisely, for 304 stainless steel, the values of $\sigma'_f, E, b, \varepsilon'_f, c$ are taken from Ref. [27]: τ'_f and γ'_f are computed as $\tau'_f = \sigma'_f / \sqrt{3}$ and $\gamma'_f = \varepsilon'_f \sqrt{3}$, respectively, $b_0 = b$ and $c_0 = c$ are assumed, and G is determined as a function of the elastic modulus E . The fatigue strengths $\sigma_{af,-1}$ and $\tau_{af,-1}$ are computed as follows:

$$\sigma_{af,-1} = \sigma'_f (2N_0)^b \quad (15)$$

$$\tau_{af,-1} = \tau'_f (2N_0)^{b_0} \quad (16)$$

By assuming $N_0 = 2 \cdot 10^6$ loading cycles, such strengths are equal to 177 MPa and 102 MPa, respectively. The ratio $\tau_{af,-1}/\sigma_{af,-1}$ is equal to 0.576, that is, the material is considered sensitive to non-proportional loading, being such a value close to $1/\sqrt{3}$. Further, ν_{eff} is taken from Ref. [28].

The computed values of k and α for such a stainless steel are equal to 0.4944 and 0.7091, respectively.

For the 6061 aluminum alloy, the coefficients of the Manson-Coffin curves are taken from Ref. [27]. The fatigue strengths computed through Eqs (15) and (16) by assuming $N_0 = 2 \cdot 10^6$ loading cycles are equal to $\sigma_{af,-1} = 230$ MPa and $\tau_{af,-1} = 134$ MPa. The ratio is $\tau_{af,-1}/\sigma_{af,-1} = 0.583$, that is, the material is considered sensitive to non-proportional loading. Further, ν_{eff} is taken from Ref. [27].

The computed values of k and α for such an aluminum alloy are equal to 0.0990 and 0.1670, respectively.

4.1 304 stainless steel: results

The computed values of φ_i and Φ_i are listed in **Table 5** for each non-proportional loading condition examined. The computed values of both $\varepsilon_{RED,a}$ and N_f are also listed in such a Table.

Table 5

Figure 5(a) shows the correlation between the experimental fatigue life N_{exp} and $\varepsilon_{RED,a}$, whereas **Figure 5(b)** shows the correlation between N_{exp} and N_f .

Figure 5

It can be noticed that 75% of the results in **Figure 5(a)** are conservative, and that the results in **Figure 5(b)** fall into the scatter band 3 (defined by the dash-dot lines) for 92% of cases. The accuracy of the criterion is also evaluated by means of the root mean square error T_{RMS} [20], which is equal to 2.13.

The results determined by applying the procedure proposed by the present authors in Ref. [20] are plotted in **Figure 6**. In such a case, 96% of the results are non-conservative, falling into the scatter band 3 for 54% of cases (**Figure 6(b)**). The value of T_{RMS} is 3.31. Therefore, a relevant improvement of the results can be obtained by applying the novel criterion.

Figure 6

The results computed by applying the method by Borodii et al. [23-25] are plotted in **Figure 7**. In such a case, the material constant k characterising the difference in the cyclic properties

with respect to those related to proportional strain path is here determined to be equal to 0.2937 , whereas the material constant α related to the additional cyclic hardening is here deduced to be equal to 0.9188 . The number of loading cycles to failure, N_f , is determined by employing Eq. (2).

Figure 7

It can be noticed that 83% of the results are non-conservative, falling into the scatter band 3 for 75% of cases (**Figure 7(b)**). The value of T_{RMS} is 2.15.

Figures 8 and **9** show the results reported in Refs **[18,19]**, obtained using two different equivalent non-proportional strain amplitudes, named $\Delta\varepsilon_{NP}/2$ (first formulation) and $\Delta\varepsilon_{NP}^*/2$ (second formulation). Details are reported in Ref. **[18]**. N_f is determined through by employing Eq. (2). It can be noticed that the results are always non-conservative, generally out of scatter band 3, and with T_{RMS} value equal to 3.14 and 3.31 when $\Delta\varepsilon_{NP}/2$ and $\Delta\varepsilon_{NP}^*/2$ are employed to calculate N_f , respectively.

Figure 8

Figure 9

4.2 6061 aluminum alloy: results

The computed values of φ_i and Φ_i are listed in **Table 6** for each non-proportional loading condition examined. The computed values of both $\varepsilon_{RED,a}$ and N_f are also listed in such a Table.

Table 6

Figure 10(a) shows the correlation between the experimental fatigue life N_{exp} and $\varepsilon_{RED,a}$, whereas **Figure 10(b)** shows the correlation between N_{exp} and N_f .

Figure 10

It can be noticed that 83% of the results in **Figure 10(a)** are conservative, and that the results in **Figure 10(b)** fall into the scatter band 3 for 75% of cases. The T_{RMS} value is equal to 2.61.

The results determined by applying the procedure proposed by the present authors in Ref. [20] are plotted in **Figure 11**. In such a case, 58% of the results are non-conservative, falling into the scatter band 3 for 83% of cases (**Figure 11(b)**). The value of T_{RMS} is 2.75. Also for such a material, a relevant improvement can be observed by applying the novel criterion.

Figure 11

The results computed by applying the method by Borodii et al. [23-25] are plotted in **Figure 12**. In such a case, the material constant k characterising the difference in the cyclic properties with respect to those related to proportional strain path is here determined to be equal to 0.2246, whereas the material constant α related to the additional cyclic hardening is here deduced to be equal to 0.4089. N_f is determined through Eq. (2).

Figure 12

It can be observed that 92% of the results are non-conservative, falling into the scatter band 3 for 33% of cases (**Figure 12(b)**), with $T_{RMS} = 4.35$.

Figures 13 and **14** show the results reported in Ref. [19], obtained using two different equivalent non-proportional strain amplitudes, named $\Delta\varepsilon_{NP}/2$ (first formulation) and $\Delta\varepsilon_{NP}^*/2$ (second formulation). Details are reported in Ref. [18]. N_f is determined through Eq. (2). It can be noticed that the results are always non-conservative, generally out of scatter band 3, and with T_{RMS} value equal to 19.26 and 25.22 when $\Delta\varepsilon_{NP}/2$ and $\Delta\varepsilon_{NP}^*/2$ are employed to calculate N_f , respectively.

Figure 13

Figure 14

5. CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper, a novel criterion for fatigue life assessment of engineering components under multiaxial low-cycle fatigue regime has been proposed. Testing results related to two metals have been examined to evaluate the accuracy of the criterion.

For the 304 stainless steel examined, it has been observed that:

- 75% of the results, in terms of N_f , are conservative;
- 92% of the estimated N_f values fall into the scatter band 3;
- the T_{RMS} value is 2.13.

For the 6061 aluminum alloy examined, it has been observed that:

- 83% of the results, in terms of N_f , are conservative;
- 75% of the estimated N_f values fall into the scatter band 3;
- the T_{RMS} value is 2.61.

Moreover, the present criterion is complete, taking into account: (i) the strain path orientation, by means of the parameter φ_i , (ii) the degree of non-proportionality, by means of the parameter Φ_i , and (iii) the changing of material cyclic properties under non-proportional loading, by means of the material constants k and α .

Although the criterion has shown better a accuracy that those of other criteria available in the literature, it has to be further validated by analysing, for example, loading characterised by a different type of non-proportionality.

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NOMENCLATURE

$\hat{1}, \hat{2}, \hat{3}$	directions of the principal strain axes at the time instant when ε_1 is maximum
E	elastic modulus
k	material constant representative of the material sensitivity to the change of fatigue properties
l_i	length of the path in the plane $\varepsilon_z - \gamma_{zt} / \sqrt{3}$
N_{exp}	experimental number of loading cycles to failure
N_f	number of loading cycles to failure
\mathbf{w}	normal vector to the critical plane
rtz	fixed frame
$S_{0,i}$	area of the smallest circle which contains the i -th convex path
$S'_{0,i}$	area of the smallest circle which contains the equivalent convex strain path
S_i	area enveloped by the i -th convex path
S'_i	area enveloped by an equivalent convex strain path containing the i -th one
T	observation time
T_{RMS}	root mean square error
uvw	local frame attached to the critical plane
α	additional cyclic hardening coefficient
γ_a	torsional Manson-Coffin equation
Δ	critical plane
$\Delta\gamma_{zt}$	range of the applied shear strain
$\Delta\varepsilon_z$	range of the applied normal strain
δ	angle defining the normal to the critical plane
$\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3$	principal strains
ε_a	tensile Manson-Coffin equation
$\varepsilon_{eq,a}^p$	equivalent deformation amplitude for proportional

	loading
$\varepsilon_{RED,a}$	refined equivalent deformation amplitude
$\boldsymbol{\eta}$	displacement vector on the critical plane
$\eta_{N,a}$	amplitude of the normal displacement vector $\boldsymbol{\eta}_N$
$\eta_{C,a}$	amplitude of the tangential displacement vector $\boldsymbol{\eta}_C$
ν_{eff}	effective Poisson's ratio
$\sigma_{af,-1}$	fully reversed normal strength
σ_{eq}^p	equivalent stress under proportional loading
σ_{eq}^{np}	equivalent stress for a sinusoidal loading with phase shift equal to 90°
$\sigma'_f, b, \varepsilon'_f, c$	coefficients of the tensile Manson-Coffin equation
$\tau_{af,-1}$	fully reversed shear strength
$\tau'_f, b_0, \gamma'_f, c_0$	coefficients of the torsional Manson-Coffin equation
Φ_i	coefficient of non-proportionality of the i -th non-proportional strain path
φ_i	angle formed by the i -th non-proportional strain path with respect to the abscissa axis in the plane ε_x - $\gamma_x/\sqrt{3}$

**The RED criterion for fatigue life assessment of metals under
non-proportional loading**

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FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure 1. Flowchart of the RED criterion.

Figure 2. Specimen made of 304 stainless steel (sizes in mm).

Figure 3. Stain paths examined [18-19]: proportional and non-proportional.

Table 1. 304 stainless steel: loading conditions and experimental fatigue life.

PATH NO.	LOADING CONDITION	$\Delta\varepsilon_z$ [%]	$\Delta\gamma_{zt}$ [%]	N_{exp} [cycles]
0	0a	0.50	-	49000
	0b	0.65	-	23400
	0c	0.80	-	7100
	0d	1.00	-	1500
	0e	1.13	-	1700
	0f	1.20	-	690
	0g	1.50	-	540
1	1a	0.50	0.87	9500
	1b	0.80	1.39	1400
2	2a	0.50	0.87	20000
	2b	0.80	1.39	2100
3	3a	0.50	0.87	2400
	3b	0.80	1.39	820
4	4a	0.50	0.87	3400
	4b	0.80	1.39	900
5	5a	0.50	0.87	17500
	5b	0.80	1.39	3200
6	6a	0.50	0.87	9700
	6b	0.80	1.39	2600
7	7a	0.50	0.87	18000
	7b	0.80	1.39	1700
8	8a	0.50	0.87	2050
	8b	0.80	1.39	470
9	9a	0.50	0.87	2950
	9b	0.80	1.39	660
10	10a	0.50	0.87	2600
	10b	0.80	1.39	320
11	11a	0.50	0.87	14400
	11b	0.80	1.39	1200
12	12a	0.50	0.87	4750
	12b	0.80	1.39	710

Figure 4. Specimen made of 6061 aluminum alloy (sizes in mm).

Table 2. 6061 aluminium alloy: loading conditions and experimental fatigue life.

PATH NO.	LOADING CONDITION	$\Delta\varepsilon_z$ [%]	$\Delta\gamma_{zt}$ [%]	N_{exp} [cycles]
0	0a	0.50	-	44500
	0c	0.80	-	2900
	0f	1.20	-	740
	0h	1.80	-	225
1	1b	0.80	1.39	955
2	2b	0.80	1.39	975
3	3c	0.57	0.98	1740
4	4c	0.57	0.98	2610
5	5c	0.57	0.98	2050
	5d	0.85	1.47	970
6	6c	0.57	0.98	3370
7	7c	0.57	0.98	2800
8	8c	0.57	0.98	1310
9	9c	0.57	0.98	890
10	10c	0.57	0.98	1650
11	11c	0.72	0.36	1310
12	12b	0.80	1.39	1250

Table 3. Mechanical and fatigue properties of the 304 stainless steel [27,28].

MATERIAL	σ'_f [MPa]	E [GPa]	b	ε'_f	c	τ'_f	G [GPa]	b_0	γ'_f	c_0	ν_{eff}
Ref.	[27]	[27]	[27]	[27]	[27]						[28]
304SS	1000	183	-0.114	0.171	-0.402	577	68.3	-0.114	0.296	-0.402	0.34

Table 4. Mechanical and fatigue properties of the 6061 aluminium alloy [27].

MATERIAL	σ'_f [MPa]	E [GPa]	b	ε'_f	c	τ'_f	G [GPa]	b_0	γ'_f	c_0	ν_{eff}
Ref.	[27]	[27]	[27]	[27]	[27]						[27]
6061 AA	369	71.5	-0.0311	0.0899	-0.4520	285	28.2	-0.0497	0.3881	-0.6423	0.33

Table 5. 304 stainless steel: φ_i and Φ_i values for each non-proportional loading condition examined. The values of $\varepsilon_{RED,a}$ and N_f are also reported.

LOADING CONDITION	φ_i [rad]	Φ_i	$\varepsilon_{RED,a}$	N_f [cycles]
1a	0.00	0.64	0.0072293	2969
1b	0.00	0.64	0.0117264	693
2a	0.00	0.64	0.0072293	2969
2b	0.00	0.64	0.0117264	693
3a	0.79	0.64	0.0080074	2165
3b	0.79	0.64	0.0126834	552
4a	0.79	0.64	0.0080074	2165
4b	0.79	0.64	0.0126834	552
6a	0.79	0.25	0.0053444	7800
6b	0.79	0.25	0.0084667	1826
7a	0.79	0.36	0.0057153	6264
7b	0.79	0.36	0.0090543	1491
8a	0.79	0.45	0.0064948	4157
8b	0.79	0.45	0.0102975	1015
9a	0.79	0.45	0.0059558	5483
9b	0.79	0.45	0.0095112	1286
10a	0.79	0.89	0.0090004	1518
10b	0.79	0.89	0.0142573	395
11a	0.47	0.69	0.0059039	5640
11b	0.47	0.69	0.0094888	1295
12a	0.00	0.89	0.0081258	2070
12b	0.00	0.89	0.0131805	494

Figure 5. Correlation between the experimental fatigue life N_{exp} of the 304 stainless steel specimens under non-proportional loading and: (a) $\epsilon_{RED,a}$; (b) the computed fatigue strength N_f ($T_{RMS} = 2.13$).

Figure 6. Correlation between the experimental fatigue life N_{exp} of the 304 stainless steel specimens under non-proportional loading and: (a) $\varepsilon_{eq,a}^p$ (calculated according to the procedure presented in Ref. [20]); (b) the computed fatigue strength N_f ($T_{RMS}=3.31$).

Figure 7. Correlation between the experimental fatigue life N_{exp} of the 304 stainless steel specimens under non-proportional loading and: (a) the strain amplitude calculated according to the procedure proposed by Borodii et al. [23-25]; (b) the computed fatigue strength N_f ($T_{RMS} = 2.15$).

Figure 8. Correlation between the experimental fatigue life N_{exp} of the 304 stainless steel specimens under non-proportional loading and: (a) the strain amplitude calculated according to the first procedure proposed by Itoh et al. [18,19]; (b) the computed fatigue strength N_f ($T_{RMS} = 3.14$).

Figure 9. Correlation between the experimental fatigue life N_{exp} of the 304 stainless steel specimens under non-proportional loading and: (a) the strain amplitude calculated according to the second procedure proposed by Itoh et al. [18,19]; (b) the computed fatigue strength N_f ($T_{RMS} = 3.31$).

Table 6. 6061 aluminum alloy: φ_i and Φ_i values for each non-proportional loading condition examined. The values of $\varepsilon_{RED,a}$ and N_f are also reported.

LOADING CONDITION	φ_i [rad]	Φ_i	$\varepsilon_{RED,a}$	N_f [cycles]
1b	0.00	0.64	0.0077152	625
2b	0.00	0.64	0.0077152	625
3c	0.79	0.64	0.0077881	600
4c	0.79	0.64	0.0077881	600
6c	0.79	0.25	0.0061239	1964
7c	0.79	0.36	0.0066791	1235
8c	0.79	0.45	0.0067189	1199
9c	0.79	0.45	0.0055837	3414
10c	0.79	0.89	0.0080819	511
11c	0.47	0.69	0.0053437	4567
12b	0.00	0.89	0.0080062	532

Figure 10. Correlation between the experimental fatigue life N_{exp} of the 6061 aluminum alloy specimens under non-proportional loading and: (a) $\epsilon_{RED,a}$; (b) the computed fatigue strength N_f ($T_{RMS} = 2.61$).

Figure 11. Correlation between the experimental fatigue life N_{exp} of the 6061 aluminum alloy specimens under non-proportional loading and: (a) $\varepsilon_{eq,a}^P$ (calculated according to the procedure presented in Ref. [20]); (b) the computed fatigue strength N_f ($T_{RMS} = 2.75$).

Figure 12. Correlation between the experimental fatigue life N_{exp} of the 6061 aluminum alloy specimens under non-proportional loading and: (a) the strain amplitude calculated according to the procedure proposed by Borodii et al. [23-25]; (b) the computed fatigue strength N_f ($T_{RMS} = 4.35$).

Figure 13. Correlation between the experimental fatigue life N_{exp} of the 6061 aluminum alloy specimens under non-proportional loading and: (a) the strain amplitude calculated according to the first procedure proposed by Itoh et al. [18,19]; (b) the computed fatigue strength N_f ($T_{RMS} = 19.26$).

Figure 14. Correlation between the experimental fatigue life N_{exp} of the 6061 aluminum alloy specimens under non-proportional loading and: (a) the strain amplitude calculated according to the second procedure proposed by Itoh et al. [18,19]; (b) the computed fatigue strength N_f ($T_{RMS} = 25.22$).